

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

BEST PRACTISES ON INFORMAL EXCHANGE SITUATIONS [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 9

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Contents

1.Introduction	3
2.Network of Co-working Spaces.....	6
3.NCS as a tool to support informal interaction inside companies.....	7
4.Cooperative games theory as a theoretical model for NCS	10
5.Requirements analysis	14
6.Some usage scenarios.....	19
7.Conclusions	22
References	22
Appendix A: Glossary of Terms	25
Appendix B: Actors and Summary of Use Cases (UC).....	27
Appendix C: Detailed description of UCs.....	30
Appendix D: Domain Model	40
Appendix E: System sequence diagrams	43
Appendix F: Contracts	44
Appendix G: Mockups.....	60

1. Introduction

According to [1], mountain areas suffer from a depopulation phenomenon due to several factors. Among them, a general lack of economic opportunities, with a consequent difficulty in pursuing professional and personal development, together with a lack of social connection possibilities, push people to move to urban areas, which provide more opportunities both from a professional perspective and from a personal and family perspective (education, elders assistance, sport facilities, shops, infrastructures). This creates a vicious cycle: as populations decline, rural areas become further impoverished. Those who remain often face long commutes, negatively impacting both their quality of life and the environment [2].

An ill-fated consequence of depopulation in mountain areas is the reduced power of innovation: the local economical and organizational models become out marketed by larger competitors, leading to the abandonment of consolidated practices and to the closure of several activities (such as small enterprises and farms) [3].

To reverse this trend and counteract depopulation, it is essential to promote social innovation, creating conditions that enhance social interactions both within individual companies and between geographically proximate businesses.

As described in [4], the term “social innovation” refers to the injection of new strategies, initiatives, processes, or organizations that meet social needs and that profoundly affect the social system in which they arise [5],[6]. Any process of social innovation consists of two dynamics that [4] calls: (1) bricolage, i.e., recombining existing and new ideas to form something novel [7],[8], and (2) contagion or diffusion, i.e., the adoption of novel ideas or inventions in broader and broader areas [5],[9]. Social innovation is a key instrument to create the conditions to revitalize the mountain areas, by supporting the locals to connect and grow opportunities for smart collaboration, by reducing the need to commute, and by attracting foreigners (to the region) to work and to use the local services.

This view of supporting social innovation heavily depends on the capabilities of incentivizing formal and informal interaction. Indeed, according to [6], some of the factors that facilitate social innovation are the promotion of both formal and informal interactions across organizational, sectoral, or

disciplinary boundaries and the empowerment of users and stakeholders to drive innovation themselves. Both the promotion of interaction and the empowerment of users/stakeholders are particularly difficult to achieve in rural settings.

We claim that a promising approach to facing the challenges described resides in the creation of specialized *Networks of Co-working Spaces* (NCS for short) that both leverage and strengthen the peculiarities of mountain/rural territories. In recent years, the emergence of co-working spaces re-shaped the working landscape, gaining widespread popularity. These spaces, designed for shared use by individual workers or small businesses, have proliferated globally. Although the COVID-19 pandemic has caused a temporary relocation of remote workers and freelancers to non-urban areas, many co-working spaces are located in large urban areas, in close proximity to clients usually highly skilled ICT professionals, freelancers, and creative-class employees [10],[13]. The scarcity of opportunities for collaboration and innovation between professionals and local businesses, and the difficulty of finding networking and professional growth opportunities, that are typically associated with small, remote communities, are seen as disadvantages. In order to overcome these disadvantages, we propose a different model: co-working spaces are reimagined as interlinked hubs, that are situated in small villages, and are designed not only to foster traditional coworking benefits, such as shared resources and communal working environments, but also to serve as focal points for socialization and both intra-company and inter-company informal interaction. By establishing these networks around core regional thematic areas, they can encourage local residents to engage deeply with their fields while also attracting external workers, who look for specialized collaborative communities. The proposed structure emphasizes local governance, ensuring that the initiatives align closely with regional development goals and that they are integrated into the local socioeconomic fabric. The co-working hubs are no more merely seen as places of work, but as active centers which foster social innovation and entrepreneurial activity. This model leverages the dynamics of shared economies and resource pooling, potentially leading to the birth of new startups, driving local employment, and contributing to a robust and resilient regional economy.

To support this vision, we propose the design of a software infrastructure that enables stakeholders to meet, socialize, and cooperate. In this deliverable, we introduce the NCS concept, then, we illustrate a game theory approach to show the added value of an NCS, and we explore the conceptual foundations of a platform aimed at supporting the creation of co-working space networks. Specifically, we provide a corpus of requirements for the development of such a platform and sketch a few scenarios of the use of the NCS.

Note that the proposed framework can be leveraged to promote both the formal and informal dimensions of interaction among remote workers. To this end, we introduce the notion of *district*, i.e., a group of stakeholders operating in a set of interlinked coworking hub. A district can be built upon a set of shared competences (see, formal interaction) or common interests (see, informal interaction). For the purpose of this deliverable, we mainly focus on the second dimension. The main aim of this deliverable is to present a conceptual framework providing a set of best practices that can be used as a basis for the development of a prototype software application. Such application should support and promote informal exchange situations among remote workers inside companies.

The appendices to this document provide a comprehensive technical documentation related to the first stages of the platform design. While designing the platform, we adopted the Unified Process software development methodology¹, which follows an agile, iterative and incremental approach.

The source code of the application being developed is available at: <https://github.com/NODES-Spoke4-UniVdA/NCS>.

More in detail, the appendices cover various aspects of the system and its design. Appendix A provides a Glossary of Terms, defining specialized terminology used in the development process for clarity. Appendix B introduces the Actors and Summary of Use Cases (UCs), outlining the key participants (users and platform) and offering a high-level summary of the primary use cases that we expect to occur in the platform. Appendix C expands on this by offering a Detailed Description of UCs, providing step-

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unified_process

by-step explanations of each use case and the interactions between the actors and the system. Appendix D focuses on the Domain Model, illustrating the key concepts, entities, and their relationships within the system's domain through diagrams. Appendix E presents System Sequence Diagrams, which visually depict the sequence of interactions between the system components for specific scenarios. Appendix F defines Contracts, specifying the responsibilities, operations, and expected behaviors for various components or actors in the system to ensure a consistent implementation. Lastly, Appendix G includes Mockups, i.e., visual representations of the system's user interfaces, providing an early look at the potential design of the final product.

2. Network of Co-working Spaces

In the literature [14] two types of co-working are described:

- i) As a shared place to work alone (“work alone together”) and
- ii) As a place to work, interact, and socialize with others.

In this deliverable, we mainly refer to the latter understanding because it fosters discussions and collaborations, hence the generation of new ideas also through informal social interactions. To create a favorable environment, we propose, as a first original contribution, the concept of Network of Co-working Spaces (or NCS). As its name suggests, an NCS is a structure that connects many co-working spaces, linking them according to their geographic proximity, and helping specialized “districts” to emerge. The NCS uses a combination of formal and informal interactions to create a dynamic and sustainable work environment. Formal interactions provide the structure and organization needed for professional collaboration, while informal interactions stimulate creativity, building social networks, and sharing innovative ideas.

More in detail, an NCS has three main characteristics:

- It supports co-working by providing a window that helps users to find co-working spaces;
- It is meant to be managed and supported by a community – indeed, we expect the NCS to be managed by local (public) mountain/rural communities or organizations;
- It supports the emergence of a structured network of districts, either based on competences or on interests shared among remote workers.

Supporting co-working means that the framework provides basic functionalities, such as showing on a map the involved co-working spaces and their descriptions and providing tools for searching co-working spaces that respect desired criteria², booking a desk or a room.

Being managed and supported by a community means that organizations from the territory will be actively involved. This is in opposition to the current trend, where most of the co-working platforms are managed by private companies. Indeed, we believe that the kind of social innovation that is required to meet the main objective of the framework (i.e., to support mountain/rural areas) can be realized only by soliciting active participation of public administrations, business/cultural/religious associations, farms, shops, and so forth, both as co-working space providers and foremost to create an ecosystem of opportunities for the clients of co-working spaces.

Supporting the emergence of a structured network of districts means helping areas to develop/express specialized expertise, based on typicalities of their own, in a way that recalls industrial districts. The difference stands in that the ones supported by the NCS will be competence districts, initially grounded on the expertise that is prominent in the area but that can quickly reconfigure, based on specific initiatives, needs, and opportunities, allowing freelancers as well as small or even micro-enterprises to join forces in a very flexible and dynamic way. Therefore, the NCS uses formal and informal interactions to achieve its goals of social innovation and revitalization of mountain communities.

3. NCS as a tool to support informal interaction inside companies

In our perspective, NCS provide companies with more than just shared workspaces, they serve as vital hubs for informal interaction among remote workers, which in turn is essential for fostering both internal dynamics and external collaborations. Companies operating within NCS benefit from the synergy created by physical proximity, shared resources, and collaborative environments, where innovation and social interaction naturally intertwine.

NCS encourages informal interaction by enabling employees from different departments or even separate companies to work in shared spaces. This proximity promotes spontaneous social exchanges, which often lead to

² See, e.g., <https://www.wework.com/> or <https://www.coworker.com/>.

creative problem-solving, idea generation, and collaboration that may not occur in more formal work settings. The relaxed atmosphere of coworking spaces encourages open communication, where informal discussions during breaks, shared lunches, or networking events can lead to new business ideas and partnerships.

NCS also provide an ideal setting for corporate team-building activities. Companies can organize retreats or creative workshops within these spaces, where employees can collaborate in a less structured environment. This not only strengthens team cohesion but also boosts productivity and creativity as individuals are more relaxed and open to new perspectives.

The potential of NCS extends beyond fostering interaction within single organizations. The physical proximity within coworking spaces fosters partnerships and synergies between companies that may not typically interact. Informal discussions during breaks, shared lunches, or networking events can lead to collaborative projects that leverage the strengths of multiple organizations. This inter-company socialization strengthens both innovation and social networks, further contributing to a dynamic and supportive work environment.

Internal units or spin-offs of existing firms can leverage NCS to explore new markets, develop innovative solutions, and address specific social issues, particularly in rural or mountainous areas. These environments provide access to shared resources, enabling even small firms or startups to thrive by collaborating on joint projects, accessing specialized expertise, and sharing infrastructure.

Moreover, NCS accelerates the growth of informal social networks that drive innovation. Companies from complementary sectors or those facing similar challenges can form strategic partnerships, supported by the physical closeness and flexible spaces that NCS offers. The result is a collaborative ecosystem where individuals from different teams or organizations can engage in cross-disciplinary projects, brainstorming sessions, and informal gatherings, all of which foster creativity and strengthen corporate ties.

To maximize the innovation potential of NCS and promote informal interaction, companies can implement several strategies, such as:

- **Organize informal brainstorming sessions:** Structured opportunities for creative exchange, like open brainstorming sessions,

allow employees to share ideas more freely, fostering creativity and innovation in relaxed settings.

- **Encourage cross-functional collaboration:** By involving employees in multidisciplinary projects, NCS facilitates the merging of diverse skills and perspectives, leading to more holistic and creative solutions to complex challenges.
- **Design shared, flexible workspaces:** Open lounges, kitchens, and collaborative areas within NCS provide natural meeting points for employees to engage in spontaneous discussions, which often spark new ideas and innovations.
- **Promote team-building activities:** Organizing and hosting team-building events, workshops, and social gatherings strengthens relationships between employees and companies, fostering a collaborative atmosphere that encourages the exchange of ideas.

By enabling these informal interactions, NCS creates environments where innovation flourishes. Informal socialization between employees not only enhances creativity but also contributes to a more connected, resilient, and competitive corporate ecosystem. The NCS model ensures that both innovation and social well-being are integral parts of company culture, driving sustainable growth while strengthening the bonds between individuals and organizations.

Concerning depopulation, co-working is an incentive for people to live and work from the mountain territory. Co-working is expected to overcome some of the limitations that affect smart working (bad impacts on personal life-work balance, lack of motivation and such like [16]). We believe that the integration with the territory of the NCS can support co-working even further, supporting a better balance with personal life and everyday duties. One of the advantages of targeting the territory as main beneficiary is that the network could be more easily integrated with additional services also requiring the collaboration between neighboring areas. For instance, public transportation can better serve and connect the different co-working spaces, as well as offer a school service connecting the main schools in the territory. Agreements with local restaurants, kindergartens, hotels and such like are encouraged as well. Moreover, this approach ensures alignment with regional development goals.

Furthermore, NCS is also a form of alternative investment for mountain regions that primarily invest in tourism because mountain tourism presents some risks: it is subject to seasonality, to climate conditions, to economy trends. NCS can attract people during the whole year, and host company meetings alongside with cultural events (seminars, conferences). Additionally, private structures (e.g., hotels) can offer their spaces for co-working with an income also during the off-season periods.

4. Cooperative games theory as a theoretical model for NCS

By using a game theory approach, we can examine how a network of co-working spaces can act as a catalyst for collaboration and cooperation, promoting community wellbeing and the local economy. We propose a model that is based on the idea of cooperation and collaboration between agents (in a broad sense, e.g., professionals, freelancers, entrepreneurs, start-ups, public bodies, institutions) within an NCS, where the objective is to maximize the added value generated by the collaboration itself. The agents (here seen as nodes of the network as well involved in the NCS can join/create coalitions (or groups) to collaborate on specific projects or share resources and knowledge. Let's consider a set of N agents from which it is possible to identify and "think" coalitions S_1 (structural, see cooperation) or S_2 (momentary, i.e. project, see collaboration) that can be thought of through a characteristic function which is responsible for evaluating the design and propositional weight in terms of the realization of an entrepreneurial output. In general, $V(S)$ is the weight of cooperation (or collaboration) for the generic coalition S which can be formed considering n agents, $N = 1 \dots n$ and we indicate by $P(N)$ the set of parts of N (coalitions). We know that this set is made up of 2^n elements (excluding the case of an empty coalition). We theorize in our cooperative co-working model that it is possible to assign a design weight $V(S)$ to each coalition $S \in P(N)$. We will then say that the co-working game is defined in characteristic form V with $V: 2^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. In particular, we have that:

$$V(S_1) + V(S_2) \leq V(S_1 \cup S_2) \quad (1)$$

The weight assigned to each coalition represents the value or contribution of that specific coalition's collaboration to the coworking network. This weight can be determined by various factors, such as complementary skills, shared resources, networking opportunities, and so on.

For all $S_1, S_2 \in P(N)$ such that $S_1 \cap S_2 = \emptyset$; we will say that the characteristic function of the game is superadditive. For all the superadditive functions generated by regulatory policies aimed at creating these shared creative spaces, animated in terms of innovation and design sustainability by the agents, it is rational to think that:

$$\sum_{i \in S} V(i) \leq V(S) \quad \forall S \in P(N) \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the superadditivity of the characteristic function implies that collaborating within a co-working network is more advantageous than acting individually, e.g., for knowledge spillovers and network externalities. This added value comes from the combination of skills, resources and different perspectives brought by the various members of the coalition forming part of the NCS. In other words, the value generated by the collaboration is greater than the sum of the values generated by the individual actions of the members of the NCS. It can be interesting to evaluate the role and the related weight (power) of each agent (node of the co-working network) in adding and/or promoting new initiatives or projects, as well. Let's consider a co-working network composed of multiple nodes spread across various regional locations. Each of these nodes has "features" (level of innovation and technology, economic-financial weight, reference industrial sector – primary, secondary, tertiary, advanced tertiary, etc.). Therefore, we believe it is useful to weigh each node to understand the power that can be generated by this system that networks many operational micro-realities. In this direction, we could model this aspect through a Shapley Value [15] defined by a value function Val of the agents in S (co-working space). The Shapley Value can be used to evaluate the contribution of each agent (or node) within a NCS. It takes into account the marginal contributions of each node when joining different coalitions, thus allowing the specific contribution of each node to be quantified to collaboration and cooperation within the network. We define a characteristic function $V(S)$ for each coalition S , which measures the value or contribution of that coalition to the co-working network. This may include factors such as complementary skills, shared resources, networking opportunities, and so on. For each agent i (or node) within the NCS, we calculate the Shapley Value using the following equation:

$$\phi_i(Val) = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! \cdot (n - |S| - 1)!}{n!} [Val(S \cup i) - Val(S)] \quad (3)$$

This approach provides a fair and complete assessment of each agent's contribution to the co-working network. In particular, equation 3 calculates the weighted average of all marginal contributions over all possible coalitions S , where:

- $\phi_i(Val)$ is the Shapley Value of the agent i , which represents its fair contribution to the co-working network. This value quantifies the specific role of each agent in the network and its impact on the overall collaboration.
- n is the total number of agents within the co-working network. This information is essential to calculate the combinatorial weight and marginal contribution of each agent.
- $\frac{|S|!(n-|S|-1)!}{n!}$ is a combinatorial weight that takes into account all possible orders of entry into the coalition. This weight ensures that each agent's contribution is valued equally across all possible coalitions in which it can participate.
- $|S|$ is the size of the subset S . This dimension is important for calculating the marginal contribution.
- $Val(S \cup i) - Val(S)$ represents the marginal contribution of agent i when joining the coalition S . This value quantifies the additional effect that agent i brings to the coalition.

Thus, the Shapley Value of an agent i represents his fair contribution to the NCS based on his marginal contributions to various coalitions. An agent with a high Shapley Value is particularly important for the network, as it makes a significant contribution to collaboration and cooperation. As we have just demonstrated, when applying the Shapley Value to an NCS, it is important to understand how each agent (or node) contributes to the network. This approach allows quantifying the specific contribution of each node to collaboration and cooperation within the network. Once the value of each node has been estimated, it is possible to calculate the total value of the NCS by aggregating the Shapley Values of each node as shown in the following equation

$$\Phi_{NCS}(Val) = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi S_i^j(.) \quad (4)$$

where $(.)$ can include parameters related to the characteristic function $V(S)$ that reflect the objectives of the NCS, such as promoting innovation, sharing resources, networking, coalition success and integration of different skills.

This allows the calculation to be adapted to the unique characteristics of the network and its nodes. Equation 4 represents the overall value of the network, taking into account the individual contribution of each node. Therefore, aggregating the Shapley Value for each node provides a fair and precise assessment of the total value of the NCS. This value represents the strength of the network in terms of collaboration, resource sharing and opportunity creation and provides a detailed and precise view of each agent's contribution to the NCS, helping to identify the key agents and collaboration dynamics that contribute the most to the success and sustainability of the network. We believe that knowing the Shapley Value of each agent can help identify which agents are most crucial to the success of the NCS and where to focus resources to maximize the value of collaboration. This suggests that the agents involved should be encouraged to cooperate and adopt collaborative strategies to maximize the benefits for all participants. In particular, the Shapley Value provides a measure of the contribution of each agent to the creation of value within the NCS, considering the various characteristics and influences that each agent brings with it. This can be helpful in better understanding each agent's role and acting fairly distribute the benefits deriving from collaboration and initiatives within the NCS, helping to guide informed decisions and promote their effectiveness and fair collaboration between all actors involved. In conclusion, the model provides a theoretical framework for understanding and promoting collaboration and cooperation within an NCS, highlighting the importance of creating synergies and added value through collaboration between different agents.

We integrate within the cooperative game theory model the effect of informal interaction as a fundamental aspect of social life that contributes significantly to the building of relationships, emotional support and the promotion of collaboration and innovation within the community. NSC. Indeed, informal interactions can increase the value of coalitions by adding a level of connections that promote information and expertise sharing, trust, and greater cohesion. Therefore, we can define a new characteristic function $V'(S)$ that incorporates this effect

$$V'(S) = V(S) + I(S) \quad (5)$$

where $I(S)$ represents the added value resulting from informal interactions within the coalition S . This value can be modeled based on the frequency,

quality and diversity of informal interactions. Therefore, we define a function $I(S)$ that combines these parameters

$$I(S) = \beta \cdot \text{frequency}(S) + \alpha \cdot \text{diversity}(S) + \gamma \cdot \text{quality}(S). \quad (6)$$

The frequency of interactions indicates the number of informal interactions between agents in a given period, while the quality of interactions indicates the depth and significance of informal interactions which can be measured through surveys or feedback. Finally, interactional diversity is understood as the variety of skills and perspectives involved in informal interactions.

$\beta, \alpha, e \gamma$ are coefficients that weight the relative importance of each parameter.

Therefore, we obtain a richer and more realistic representation of the cooperation dynamics within a NSC.

We reformulate the Shapley Value, considering the contribution of informal interactions, as follows:

$$\phi_i(Val') = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! \cdot (n - |S| - 1)!}{n!} [Val'(S \cup i) - Val'(S)] \quad Val'(S) \quad (7)$$

This approach provides a more comprehensive assessment of each agent's contribution, taking into account both formal and informal interactions. Therefore, the proposed model recognizes the value of informal interactions and their impact on value creation, facilitating a deeper understanding of collaboration dynamics and strategies to promote social innovation.

5. Requirements analysis

The proposal of NCS that we are making is novel, to the best of our knowledge, and no specific technological platform exists that can support its development. In this section, we list a set of requirements to its realization, following the MoSCoW (Must-have - Should-have - Could-have - Won't-have (yet)) prioritization approach:

- **Must have** - They represent non-negotiable needs for the project, product, or release in question;
- **Should have** - Important features that are not vital, but add significant value;
- **Could have** - Nice to have features that will have small impact if left out;
- **Will not have** - Some initiatives in the “will-not-have” group will be prioritized in the future, while others are not likely to happen.

Each requirement's label begins with 'M', 'S', 'C', or 'W' depending on the case. Since the NCS is a network of co-working spaces, part of the requirements will concern the physical spaces themselves and part will concern the software application (platform in the following) that is used for management and human networking.

The MoSCoW prioritization approach addresses both formal interactions, necessary for the structure and organization of co-working, and informal interactions, crucial for strengthening relationships, sharing knowledge and social innovation. It is worth noting that for the purpose of this deliverable, we give higher priority to those aspects related to the establishment of informal interaction opportunities among workers inside a specific company as well as across different ones.

Physical and Hardware Requirements

- M1: Flexible Workspaces - Adjustable furniture and partitions would accommodate various work styles and preferences.
- M2: Meeting Spaces - Meeting rooms, equipped with projectors, screens, whiteboards, etc. would support group work.
- M3: Recreational Facilities and other Local Services – Some examples are: communal kitchens, lounge, outdoor recreational space, pick-up and delivery points, public administration contact points, kindergartens, etc.
- M4: Co-living spaces - The presence of co-living spaces (even thanks to agreements with accommodation providers, like hotels or B&Bs) would attract corporate managers and digital nomads looking for a comprehensive experience in territories with an important environmental heritage.
- S1: Reliable Communication - High-speed internet access, either from optical fiber connection (FTTC or FTTH) or cellular network coverage (5G) are essential for remote work. Satellite internet may be necessary in areas with limited infrastructure and poor coverage. For each registered facility, the platform must allow users to know the kind of network connection that is offered.
- S2: Workspace Equipment - Ergonomic desks and chairs, specific hardware or software, adequate lighting, and temperature control are essential to ensure a comfortable and productive work environment. The platform

must allow facility providers to specify the equipment available in their facility, so that workers can select the ones that best suit their needs.

S3: Networking Infrastructure - Wired/wireless networking equipment, VPNs, etc. to support connectivity within the co-working space and with external networks. The coworking space description should make available to its users all the necessary information/guidelines for use.

S4: Environmental Sustainability - Energy-efficient appliances, solar panels, and waste management systems to minimize the environmental impact of the co-working space.

C1: Outdoor Workspace - Sheltered outdoor areas with seating and Wi-Fi access, allowing co-workers to enjoy the natural surroundings while working.

C2: Remote Monitoring and Security Systems – Surveillance and remote monitoring devices to enhance security.

C3: Backup Power Supply - In regions prone to power outages, having backup generators or uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) can prevent disruptions to work during emergencies.

Software Platform Functional Requirements

M1: User Registration and Profile Management - End users may be either individuals (workers), groups (e.g. companies, project-oriented groups) or facility providers. Registration and profile creation are necessary to identification and proper management. Individual/group profiles may include skills, professional interests, and current location (all possibly varying along time). If only individuals are tackled, we fall in the model “each one works apart”.

M2: Security and Privacy - Data and interactions must be tackled with utmost attention to privacy and security.

M3: Ontology-Based Search Tools - The platform must provide advanced search tools to find users (of any kind) or resources that exploit the full-fledged range of profile and activity descriptions, location description, local services description, area description and, where available, agreements with local facilities (shops, restaurants, kindergartens, ...).

M4: Feedback and Rating System - The platform must include a reviewing system to build trust and reliability within the network.

- M5: Event Management Tools - The platform must provide tools that support organization and advertisement of thematic events, such as workshops, seminars, and collaborative projects.
- M6: Booking and Management tools - The platform must support users in booking a workplace, shared resources, meeting rooms.
- M7: Local Smart Collaboration Support - Provide tools that help the users of a co-working space to find each other, join and start new (goal-oriented) collaborations in order to benefit from emerging opportunities, to face new needs or to innovate.
- M8: Global Smart Collaboration Support - Provide tools that support planning activities that span over two or more co-working spaces, elicit value-chain synergies.
- M9: Map Exploration Tools - The ability to show on a map the competencies that can be found at the geographically located co-working spaces at a certain moment in time (and the availability of the involved persons to be contacted) is a vital tool, that helps co-working spaces users to decide where and when they can find the desired support or discuss new projects.
- S1: Interest-Based Discussion Channels - The platform should offer channels or groups based on shared personal interests (e.g., hobbies, sports, books, travel) where remote workers can join and interact, creating a space for informal bonding around topics outside of work.
- S2: Team-Building Event Scheduling - The platform should support the scheduling of virtual team-building events like trivia, games, or wellness activities (e.g., virtual yoga or meditation) that can help strengthen team cohesion even when employees are physically distant.
- S3: Informal Meetups for Cross-Team Interaction - Facilitate informal virtual meetups where members from different teams can interact and discuss topics that aren't directly related to their work. This can foster cross-functional collaboration and help employees feel more connected across the company.
- S4: Personal Milestone Celebrations - Allow users to share and celebrate personal milestones (e.g., birthdays, work anniversaries, major life events) via the platform, helping remote workers feel recognized and

valued even from a distance. This could be done through shoutouts, virtual cards, or even organized celebrations.

S5: Mentorship and Buddy System - Implement a feature that matches new remote employees with experienced ones for mentorship or buddy programs, encouraging both professional growth and informal support systems.

S6: Casual Interest-Based Competitions - Introduce non-work-related competitions based on shared interests (e.g., fitness challenges, book reading contests, photography competitions) where employees can participate, share their progress, and bond through friendly competition.

S7: Off-Work Event Coordination - Provide tools for employees to organize off-work activities, such as virtual happy hours, remote watch parties, or book clubs. The platform can offer pre-designed templates to help simplify organizing such events.

S8: Randomized "Meet Someone New" Feature - The platform could randomly match employees across departments for brief one-on-one virtual chats, encouraging connections and informal networking among remote workers who might not typically interact.

S9: Virtual Watercooler Chat - Create a virtual watercooler space where employees can drop in to have spontaneous, unstructured conversations, much like the impromptu talks that happen in physical office environments.

S10: Regional or Cultural Group Spaces - Enable employees to join region or culture-based groups, allowing for informal interaction around shared cultural backgrounds or geographical locations, which can foster a sense of belonging and encourage discussions about local events or common interests.

C1: Guidelines for New Users - The platform should provide guidelines for all prospective or actual kinds of users, e.g., how to set up a co-working space, how to join the NCS, how to search for a desk/room at a co-working space which provides certain features, how to promote an event, how to take agreements with a co-working space to offer a side service (such as lunch at a discounted price).

C2: Collaborative Software Integration - Software tools for project management, document sharing, videoconferencing and asynchronous participation, that would facilitate remote collaboration among co-workers, could be integrated in the platform.

C3: AI Recommendations - The ultimate aim of the proposal resides in empowering the human and making mountain/rural regions more attractive to workers, thus contrasting depopulation. The introduction of specific AI-driven tools, which make certain activities easier and foster smart collaboration might be helpful.

C4: Virtual Coffee Break Rooms - The platform should provide dedicated virtual spaces where employees can take short breaks, mimicking the concept of a coffee break in an office environment. These rooms can be randomly matched or topic-focused to encourage casual conversation and knowledge sharing, helping to build relationships in a non-work context.

W1: Gamification - Features such as badges, leader-boards, and achievements, usually introduced to increase users' engagement and participation, are of secondary importance in the described system. They might introduce an adversarial mind, and their introduction should be considered carefully.

These features aim to facilitate a sense of community, foster relationships, and promote informal interactions among remote workers within the company. Note that the term district does not appear in the requirements. The reason is that being a district is an emergent property of a co-working space or of an area, depending on who uses the co-working spaces of the area and the activities such persons carry out. Only by locating on a map the related competencies/skills it will be possible to say an area is a district. Such property can change over time.

6. Some usage scenarios

The availability, or the implementation, of such features, according to the prioritization given above, enables a wide spectrum of usage scenarios. We now briefly suggest a few (non-exhaustive) interactions that we expect to occur within an NCS. Mainly they will involve persons who are interested in establishing collaborations, in sharing expertise (offering their own), and in

social and informal activities as well. Further details are given in Appendix Appendix C: Detailed description of UCs.

Team Building. Company A organizes an off-site gathering / a team building event, three-days-long, to concentrate on its business, improve its practices and evolve as an organization. The perfect mix of physical and technological assets, local competences and cultural/touristic resources allows the participants to relax, enjoy the surroundings, and be more creative and productive

Digital Nomads Meet-up. A group of digital nomads organize a working week at an alpine location off-season, exploiting offers for accommodation and meals from local facilities that have an agreement with the NCS.

Remote Worker Peer Support Group. A group of remote workers from different companies form a support network within the NCS to discuss challenges related to work-life balance, productivity, and remote communication tools. These informal conversations build stronger connections and may evolve into collaborative efforts.

Health & Wellness Events. A health startup hosts weekly wellness events, such as yoga and meditation, at the NCS. These events provide an opportunity for informal interaction between professionals, helping to break down barriers and foster deeper connections.

Cross-Industry Mentorship. Company B, a tech firm in cybersecurity, hosts an informal mentorship program where experts share their knowledge with startups from other sectors using the NCS. This encourages networking and learning while opening doors for future professional alliances.

Cross-Company Hackathon. Multiple companies within the NCS organize a hackathon to solve industry-specific challenges. The event brings together professionals from different sectors - engineering, healthcare, and finance - who can informally collaborate and potentially create joint ventures.

Local Expertise Consultation. An international firm, seeking local market insight for a new product launch, connects with smaller companies and freelancers at the NCS. Informal chats over lunch lead to valuable insights and partnerships, allowing the international firm to better navigate regional preferences.

Creative Brainstorming Sessions. Freelancers working in creative industries such as writing, video editing, and marketing use NCS spaces to

hold informal brainstorming sessions. This allows them to pitch ideas to one another and develop joint marketing strategies that can benefit all parties.

Inter-Company Knowledge Exchange. Company C from the logistics industry arranges informal knowledge-sharing sessions with Company D from fintech, both using the same NCS. This interaction helps both companies learn new methods in data management and optimize their processes in unexpected ways.

Joint Research Opportunities. Two companies from different sectors, one in healthcare and another in software development, use the NCS to hold informal research meetings. By collaborating on AI applications in healthcare, they develop a joint research project that benefits both industries.

Family Needs. Andrea is the single parent of a small child, who would like to live close to the family. Andrea is a programmer and can work remotely but home does not include a proper working space. The NCS can provide a working space close to home, to family, to the kindergarten, where Andrea will have the chance to socialize both from a working and from a personal perspective.

Project Proposal. Company A would like to participate to a regional call for funding, but it lacks competence in data analysis. It looks for a local district that covers the required skills, finds and contacts a few alternatives.

Freelancer Collaboration Hub. A group of freelancers from different industries - writing, photography, and web development - use the NCS for project-based collaboration. They connect through informal coffee breaks and end up forming a team to work together on a new media campaign for a local company.

Skill-Sharing Workshop. Company B, a startup specializing in graphic design, sets up a workshop within the NCS, inviting local and remote designers from various industries to collaborate, exchange skills, and showcase their work. This not only fosters learning but also creates potential cross-company collaborations.

Professional Update. Company B uses the conference rooms offered by the co-working spaces in the NCS for presenting its latest products to the professionals working in the area and involved in the NCS.

Serendipity. Start-up D uses the networking opportunities offered by the NCS to strengthen its business idea and weave connections with local and foreign professionals, local and foreign companies, that use the same spaces.

Touristic Facilities. Hotel Alps, which would close offseason, joins the NCS offering not only rooms for coworking but also accommodation, meals, and guided tours with the support of local guides.

These scenarios demonstrate how NCS can support the creation of informal interactions that lead to collaboration, social engagement, and the exchange of knowledge across companies and industries.

7. Conclusions

We have proposed a novel socio-technical framework to promote social innovation in areas where isolation and lack of adequate infrastructures push young generations to move to urban areas, and thus to contrast depopulation, impoverishment, and disappearance of traditional culture. The framework consists in the realization of a network of co-working spaces (NCS).

The NCS uses a combination of formal and informal interactions to create a dynamic and sustainable working environment, promoting social innovation and counteracting the depopulation of mountain areas.

This deliverable summarizes how we modeled its effects by way of game theory. It also collects a set of requirements on the software platform that could help realize the framework in practice and sketches a few possible application scenarios. The integration of co-working spaces within mountain communities, supported by the increasing digital transition, offers a promising pathway to revitalize these areas by transforming them into vibrant centers of social and economic activity. This process involves both formal and informal interactions, which are critical to the success of the network.

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Appendix A: Glossary of Terms

In the Unified Process, the glossary is a comprehensive list of terms and their definitions. It serves as a reference to ensure that all stakeholders have a common understanding of the terminology used throughout the project.

Word	Description	Synonyms
Actors		
Admin	The person that can controls everything	
Business	Regional company providing useful services to users (for example hotels, b&b, refuges, firms, shops, restaurants, kindergartens) that can create initiatives and groups	Business, organization, facility
Agent	The person that uses the service (can specify personal competences , professional interests , current location and the availability to be contacted)	Workers, individuals
User	Generic user of the service (has a role between: admin, user, business)	Stakeholder
Application domain		
Initiative	Activity made for the agents . It can be shared between one or more hubs	
Interests	Field of the world that makes someone want to be involved in it	
Competences	Field of the world that someone has studied or that they work in	Skill
Resource	A physical object or place useful for the agents . It can be reserved	
Desk	A place to work	
Room	A private place	
Meeting room	A special kind of room that can accommodate many agents	

Group	A set of users that work together sharing resources and knowledge	Coalition, collaboration
Hub	A place to work, interact and socialize. Has features (such as the kind of network connection offered, the equipment available, necessary information/guidelines, the presence of rooms) and reviews	Center, co-working spaces, node
District	A group of hubs with similar competences that can quickly reconfigure	Network
Calendar	A calendar where are shown all the promotion of social initiatives, seminars and events useful for the user and all the resources they have booked	
Map	Map that shows all the hubs and their descriptions and all agreements with local businesses	
Registration	Creation of a new user	
Profile management	Changing the information present in the user's profile	
Interactions	Dialogues and collaborations between agents	
Search	Searching a hub or an agent with desired criteria. Ontology-based	
Offer a facility	Adding to the pool of locations a new facility linked to one or more hubs	
Book/Cancel the booking	Booking a desk , meeting room, resource or a room or removing the reservation	
Reviews	Reviewing system for the hubs that can be accessed by the agents that had past experiences in the space	

Create/Remove a group	Creating a group (by specifying who can participate, what is the subject and other details) or removing it	
Join/Exit a group	Agents can also join or exit an already existing group	
Add/Remove an initiative	Creating an initiative (by specifying who can participate, what is the subject, where and when it is executed and other details) or removing it. This operation changes the calendar	
Unsubscribe	Flagging a user as unsubscribed and removing their presence from the calendar and all the groups	

Appendix B: Actors and Summary of Use Cases (UC)

In the Unified Process, a brief description of use cases provides an overview of how users interact with the system to achieve specific goals. It provides enough information to understand the purpose and scope of the use case without going into detailed steps.

Actors

Main Actors: Agent, Admin, Business

Supporting Actors: none

Out of Scene Actors: none

Brief Descriptions of the UCs

Actors	Brief Descriptions of the UC
User	<p>SEARCH HUBS</p> <p>Searching a hub means to look for various options on the map, reading the descriptions of various hubs and finding the one with more desired criteria.</p> <p>MEETING PEOPLE</p>

	<p>For a user meeting people means searching other agents using their description as a guideline and trying to chat with them.</p> <p>NEW GROUP</p> <p>Creating a new group means that one of the users can create a group chat and invite other agents to join it.</p> <p>CREATING ANNOUNCEMENT</p> <p>Create an announcement means to add to the bulletin board one invite to other users with the required criteria to participate in an activity.</p>
Agent	<p>BOOKING</p> <p>Booking means to reserve a resource offered inside the network for a period of time.</p>
Business	<p>CREATING INITIATIVE</p> <p>Create an initiative means to send a request for the admin specifying the date, space and subject of it.</p> <p>OFFERING FACILITY</p> <p>Offering facilities means to add, to the pool of services present in a district, spaces useful to create new hubs, rooms or other attractions and linking them to other hubs. The changes must be approved by an admin.</p> <p>MANAGE RESOURCES</p> <p>Businesses can manage their resources by flagging their initiatives or bookings as canceled and freeing the resources.</p>
Admin	<p>EDIT CALENDAR</p> <p>Editing the calendar means flagging some initiatives or bookings as canceled and freeing the resources or approving pending request from businesses.</p>

Appendix C: Detailed description of UCs

In the Unified Process, detailed descriptions of use cases provide a comprehensive narrative of how users (actors) interact with the system to achieve specific goals. Each use case describes a sequence of actions, including alternative and exception flows, that an actor performs to complete a task.

Search hubs UC

General information

UC name: Search hubs

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: User

Stakeholders: None

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in.

Post-conditions: All the hubs with the criteria chosen are shown to the user.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to search a hub	Gives a form
2	Enters the competences and interests needed	Gives back a map that shows the active hubs with the given criteria
	Repeat from point 2 until satisfied	
3	Clicks on one of the hubs	Gives the hub's details

Extension 2a

#	Actor	System
2a	Enters the resources required in the form	Gives back a map that shows the active hubs with the given criteria

Extension 2b

#	Actor	System
2b	Enters the location required	Gives back a map that shows the active hubs with the given criteria

Meeting people UC

General information

UC name: Meeting people

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: User

Stakeholders: None

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in.

Post-conditions: The group chat is registered.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to search an agent	Gives a form
2	Enters the nickname in the form	Gives the account's details
	Repeat from point 2 until satisfied	
3	Asks to stat a chat with the account's owner	Gives a group where they can chat

Extension 2a

#	Actor	System
2a.1	Enters the competences and the interests required in the form	Gives the list of all the accounts with all the characteristics required
2a.2	Clicks on the account	Gives the account's details

Exception 2.a

#	Actor	System
2.a	Enters the nickname in the form	Notifies the user that no active agents correspond with the given nickname

New group UC

General information

UC name: New group

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: User

Stakeholders: None

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in.

Post-conditions: The new group is registered.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to create a new group	Gives a page where they can chat named automatically
2	Ask to add a new participant	Gives a form
3	Enters the nicknames in the form	Sends a confirmation that an invite has been sent to the user
	Repeat from point 2 until satisfied	

Extension (2-3)a

#	Actor	System
(2-3)a.1	Asks to edit the group	Gives a form with the old name and description of the group
(2-3)a.2	Edit the name and description	Sends a confirmation that the changes are saved

Exception 3.a

#	Actor	System
3.a	Enters the nicknames in the form	Notifies the user that some of the active agents don't correspond with the given nicknames

Creating announcement UC

General information

UC name: Creating announcement

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: User

Stakeholders: Admin

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in. At least one of the admins must be in the system.

Post-conditions: The initiative is added to the calendar.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to create an announcement	Gives a form
2	Enters the name, the period, the location, the competences and interests involved and the description of the announcement	Sends the request to the admins and returns the outcome
3	Confirms that the announcement can be shared	Confirms that the announcement has been added to the bulletin board

Extension 3a

#	Actor	System
3a	Cancels the event	Sends the cancellation to the admins

Booking UC

General information

UC name: Booking

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: Agent

Stakeholders: None

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in.

Post-conditions: The resource is booked and added to the calendar of the user.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to book something	Gives back a form
2	Enters the name of the hub or the business	Gives back a map that shows the hub or the business and a form for the resource
3	Selects the period of the booking and the type and quantity of the resource	Gives a list of resources of that type that are free in that period
	Repeat from point 2 until satisfied	
4	Clicks on one resource	Gives a form for the transaction
5	Completes the form	Notifies that the transaction is successful

Extension (2-3)a

#	Actor	System
(2-3)a.1	Enters the type of the resource and the period of the booking	Gives back a map that shows all the hubs or the businesses that own the resource
(2-3)a.2	Clicks on one of the points	Gives a list of resources of the type chosen and that are free in the period chosen

Extension 4b

#	Actor	System
4b.1	Ask to see the description of one item	Show the description
4b.2	Repeat from point 4	

Exception 2.a

#	Actor	System
2.a.1	Enters the name of the hub or the business	Notifies the user that no active hub or business correspond with the given name
2.a.2	Repeat from point 2	

Exception (2-3)a.1.a

#	Actor	System
(2-3)a.1.a	Enters the type of the resource and the period of the booking	Notifies the user that the resource selected is unavailable in the period chosen

Exception 3.a

#	Actor	System
3.a.1	Selects the period of the booking and the type and quantity of the resource	Notifies the user that the resource selected is unavailable in the period chosen
3.a.2	Repeat from point 3	

Exception 5.a

#	Actor	System
5.a	Completes the form	Notifies that the transaction is unsuccessful

Creating initiative UC

General information

UC name: Creating initiative

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: Business

Stakeholders: Admin

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in. At least one of the admins must be in the system.

Post-conditions: The initiative is added to the calendar.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to create an initiative	Gives a form
2	Enters the name, the period, the location and the description of the initiative	Sends the request to the admins and returns the outcome
3	Confirms that the initiative can happen	Adds the initiative to the calendar and shows it to everyone

Extension 3a

#	Actor	System
3a	Cancels the event	Sends the cancellation to the admins

Offering facility UC

General information

UC name: Offering facility

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: Business

Stakeholders: Admin

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in. At least one of the admins must be in the system.

Post-conditions: The facility is added to the map.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to offer a facility	Gives a form
2	Enters the name, the type, the location and the description of the facility	Sends the request to the admins and returns the outcome
3	Confirms that the facility can be added	Adds the facility to the map

Extension 3a

#	Actor	System
3a	Cancels the offer	Sends the cancellation to the admins

Manage resources UC

General information

UC name: Manage Resources

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: Business

Stakeholders: None

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in.

Post-conditions: The calendar is updated.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to edit the calendar	Shows the calendar
2	Clicks on one initiative	Shows the details of the initiative and asks if it needs to be canceled
3	Optionally cancels the initiative	Notifies that the change has been made
	Repeat from point 2 until satisfied	

Extension (2-3)a

#	Actor	System
(2-3)a.1	Clicks on one booking	Shows the details of the booking and asks if it needs to be canceled
(2-3)a.2	Optionally says that the booking is canceled	Notifies the agent of the change and updates the calendar

Edit calendar UC

General information

UC name: Edit calendar

Scope: System

Level: User objective

Main Actor: Admin

Stakeholders: Business, Agent

Preconditions: The actor must be logged in.

Post-conditions: The calendar is updated.

Main success scenario

#	Actor	System
1	Asks to edit the calendar	Shows the calendar
2	Clicks on one initiative	Shows the details of the initiative and asks if it needs to be approved or canceled
3	Optionally approves the initiative	Notifies the business of the change
	Repeat from point 2 until satisfied	

Extension (2-3)a

#	Actor	System
(2-3)a.1	Clicks on one booking	Shows the details of the booking and asks if it needs to be canceled
(2-3)a.2	Optionally says that the booking is canceled	Notifies the agent of the change and updates the calendar

Extension 3a

#	Actor	System
3a	Optionally disapproves initiative	Notifies the business of the change

Extension 3b

#	Actor	System
3b	Optionally cancels the initiative	Notifies the business of the change and updates the calendar of all users

Appendix D: Domain Model

In the Unified Process, the domain model is a conceptual representation of the real-world entities and their relationships within a specific problem domain. It is illustrated using class diagrams that capture the key concepts, attributes, and associations.

Appendix E: System sequence diagrams

In the Unified Process, system sequences are used to illustrate the interactions between the user and the system for a particular use case. These sequences are depicted using sequence diagrams, which show the flow of messages between actors (users or other systems) and the system components.

System sequence diagram of the Creating announcement UC

System sequence diagram of the Booking UC

System sequence diagram of the Creating initiative UC

System sequence diagram of the Offering facility UC

System sequence diagram of the Manage resources UC

System sequence diagram of the Edit calendar UC

Appendix F: Contracts

In the Unified Process, contracts are used to define and manage the interactions between various system components. They specify the obligations, benefits, and rights of the involved parties, ensuring clear communication and expectations. Contracts include detailed descriptions of the preconditions, postconditions, and invariants for each interaction or operation, helping to maintain consistency and correctness throughout the software development lifecycle.

Contracts for the UC “Search hub”

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *us* of User.

1. askToSearchHub()

Preconditions:

- *us* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

2. selectHubCriteria(competences: listOfCompetences, interests: listOfInterests)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “criteria”

Post-conditions:

- A map containing the searched hubs is displayed.

2a. selectHubByResources(resources: listOfResources)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “resources”

Post-conditions:

- A map containing the searched hubs is displayed.

2b. selectHubByLocation(location: coordinates)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “location”

Post-conditions:

- A map containing the searched hub is displayed.

3. chooseHub(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The hub that has hub.name = name has been clicked.

Post-conditions:

- The details of the selected hub are displayed.

Contracts for the UC “Meeting people”

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *us* of User.

1. askToSearchAgent()

Preconditions:

- *us* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

2. selectAgent(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “name”

Post-conditions:

If the agent exists:

- The details of the agent are displayed.

Else:

- A error message warning *us* that the agent doesn't exist is displayed.

2a.1. selectAgentCriteria(competences: listOfCompetences, interests: listOfInterests)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “criteria”

Post-conditions:

- A list of agents with the selected criteria is displayed.

2a.2. selectAgent(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The agent that has agent.name = name has been clicked.

Post-conditions:

- The details of the agent are displayed.

3. askToChat(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The agent that has agent.name = name must be selected.

Post-conditions:

- A group page is displayed.

Contracts for the UC “New group”

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *us* of User.

1. askToCreateGroup()

Preconditions:

- *us* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A new group page is displayed with an instance *gr* of Group.

- *us* is **part of** *gr*.

2. askToAddAgent()

Preconditions:

- *us* must be **part of** *gr*.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

3. selectAgentName(name: name)

Preconditions:

- *us* must be **part of** *gr*.

Post-conditions:

If the agent exists:

- A confirmation message is displayed.

Else:

- A error message warning *us* that the agent doesn't exist is displayed.

(2-3)a.1.askToEditGroup(name: name)

Preconditions:

- *us* must be **part of** *gr*.
- The group that needs to be edited is *gr* and *gr.name* = name.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

(2-3)a.2.editGroup(name: string, description: string)

Preconditions:

- *us* must be **part of** *gr*.
- The agent that has agent.name = name has been clicked.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *gr.name* = name.
- *gr.purpose* = description.

Contracts for the UC "Creating announcement"

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *us* of User.

1. askAddAnnouncement()

Preconditions:

- *us* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

2. specifyAnnouncementDetails(name: string, date: date, location: coordinates, competences: listOfCompetences, interests: listOfInterests, description: string)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A new announcement is added with an instance *an* of Announcement.

- $an.open = n$.
- $an.name = name$.
- $an.date = date$.
- $an.location = location$.
- $an.description = description$.
- The outcome of the decision made by the admins is displayed.

3. confirmAnnouncement(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The announcement that has $an.name = name$ is not cancelled.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- an is **inside** the bulletin board.
- $an.open = y$.

3a. cancelAnnouncement(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A deletion message is displayed.
- $an.cancelled = y$.

Contracts for the UC "Booking"

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance ag of Agent.

1. askBook()

Preconditions:

- ag must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

2. selectBookingLocation(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “location”.

Post-conditions:

If the information is correct:

- A map containing the searched hubs and a form is displayed.
- A item *it* is created.
- *it.booked* = *n*.

Else:

- A error message warning *us* that the location doesn't exist.

3. chooseResource(type: name, quantity: number, start: date, end: date)

Preconditions:

- The item *it* must exist.

Post-conditions:

If the resource is available:

- A list containing the resources with the selected criteria is displayed.
- The resource that has resource.name = type **is represented** by *it*.
- *it.quantity* = quantity.
- *it.start* = start.
- *it.end* = end.

Else:

- A error message warning *ag* that the resource is unavailable.

(2-3)a.1. choosesResource(type: name, quantity: number, start: date, end: date)

Preconditions:

- The method of search selected must be “resource”.

Post-conditions:

If the resource is available:

- A map containing the hubs that offer the resources with the selected criteria is displayed.
- A item *it* is created.

- The resource that has `resource.name = type` **is represented** by *it*.
- *it.quantity* = quantity.
- *it.start* = start.
- *it.end* = end.

Else:

- A error message warning *ag* that the resource is unavailable.

(2-3)a.2. selectTheBookingLocation(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The item *it* must exist.

Post-conditions:

- A list containing the resources with the selected criteria is displayed.

4. chooseOneResource(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The resource that has `resource.name = name` has been clicked.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

5. sendCardInfo(number: string, code: number, owner: string)

Preconditions:

- The resource that has `resource.name = name` has been clicked.

Post-conditions:

If the information is correct:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *it.booked* = y.
- calendar **contains** *it*.

Else:

- A error message warning *ag* that the transaction is unsuccessful.

Contracts for the UC "Creating initiative"

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *bu* of Business.

1. askAddInitiative()

Preconditions:

- *bu* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

2. specifyInitiativeDetails(name: string, start: date, end: date, location: coordinates, description: string)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A new Initiative is added with an instance *in* of Initiative.
- A item *it* is created **as a** *in*.
- *in.subject* = name.
- *in.location* = location.
- *in.description* = description.
- *it.start* = start.
- *it.end* = end.
- The outcome of the decision made by the admins is displayed.

3. confirmInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- The announcement that has *in.name* = name is not cancelled.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *in* is **inside** the bulletin board.

3a. cancellInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A deletion message is displayed.
- *in.cancelled* = y.

Contracts for the UC “Offer Facility”

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *bu* of Business.

1. askOfferFacility()

Preconditions:

- *bu* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A form is displayed.

2. specifyFacilityDetails(name: string, type: string, location: coordinates, description: string)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A new facility is added with an instance *fa* of Facility.
- *bu* **possesses** *fa*.
- *fa.name* = name.
- *fa.location* = location.
- *fa.description* = description
- The outcome of the decision made by the admins is displayed.

3. confirmFacilityAddition(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *fa* is **displayed in** the map.

3a. cancelFacility(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- *fa*.cancelled = y.
- A deletion message is displayed.

Contracts for the UC “Manage resources”

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *bu* of Business.

1. askManageResources()

Preconditions:

- *bu* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- The calendar is displayed.

2. chooseInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- At least one initiative must be displayed.

Post-conditions:

- The details of the initiative are displayed. An instance *it* of Item is the representation of the initiative.

3. cancelsInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *it*.cancelled = y.

(2-3)a.1. chooseBooking(name: name)

Preconditions:

- At least one booking must be displayed.

Post-conditions:

- The details of the booking are displayed. An instance *it* of Item is the representation of the booking.

(2-3)a.2. cancelBooking(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *it.cancelled* = y.
- *it.booked* = n.

Contracts for the UC “Edit calendar”

General precondition: the actor is identified with an instance *ad* of Admin.

1. askEditCalendar()

Preconditions:

- *ad* must be logged in.

Post-conditions:

- A the calendar is displayed.

2. chooseInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- At least one initiative must be displayed.

Post-conditions:

- The details of the initiative (*in* is an instance of Initiative) are displayed. An instance *it* of Item is the representation of the initiative.

3. approveInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *in.approved* = y.

3a. disapproveInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *in*.approved = n.

3b. cancelInitiative(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *it*.cancelled = y.

(2-3)a.1. chooseBooking(name: name)

Preconditions:

- At least one booking must be displayed.

Post-conditions:

- The details of the booking are displayed. An instance *it* of Item is the representation of the booking.

(2-3)a.2. cancelBooking(name: name)

Preconditions:

- None.

Post-conditions:

- A confirmation message is displayed.
- *it*.cancelled = y.
- *it*.booked = n.

Appendix G: Mockups

The user will start by logging in their account to access the site.

In the home page they will be able to choose what actions they want to do.

In the chat page they will be able to contact other users to organize and share common activities.

If the user wants to book something they can search the resource near a certain location or by specifying what kind of resource they need and when they want to book it.

The screenshot displays the NODES search interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for Booking, My Calendar, Bulletin Board, Chat, and Notifications. The main search area includes a form with the following fields:

- Type: A text input field.
- Quantity: A text input field.
- Start: A calendar for May 2024 with dates from 01 to 31.
- Finish: A calendar for May 2024 with dates from 01 to 31.

To the right of the form is a map showing a street grid with several location pins. Below the form and map are 'Cancel' and 'Search' buttons. The footer contains the NODES logo, company information, a help center, and contact info.

COMPANY

- About Us
- Legal Information
- Contact Us
- Blogs

HELP CENTER

- Find a Property
- How To Host?
- Why Us?
- FAQs
- Rental Guides

CONTACT INFO

- Phone: 1234567890
- Email: company@email.com
- Location: 100 Smart Street, LA, USA

Social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn are also present.

If they choose to search using the location, a map will be shown and then they will be able to choose the parameters of the booking.

Resources

The screenshot displays the NODES application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the NODES logo and several menu items: Booking, My Calendar, Bulletin Board, Chat, and Notifications. A user profile icon is visible on the right. Below the navigation bar, the text '6 Results Found' is displayed next to a 'Filters' button. The main content area shows a grid of search results. Two results are visible, each for a 'Well Furnished Apartment' located at '100 Smart Street, LA, USA'. Each listing includes a 'Listed By' section with a teal circular profile picture and the name 'John Doberman', along with a price range of '\$ 1000 - \$ 5000'. Below the listing title, there are icons representing amenities: a bed for 3, a chair for 1, a car for 2, and a group of people for 0. At the bottom of each listing, it says 'Apartment on Rent' and 'For Long Period: 1 - 2 Years'. The interface is clean and modern, with a white background and teal accents.

A list of resources corresponding to the parameters previously selected will be shown.

The screenshot displays the NODES website interface. At the top, there are navigation links: "Booking", "My Calendar", "Bulletin Board", "Chat", and "Notifications". A user profile icon is visible in the top right corner. Below the navigation, the page title "Resources" is shown. The main content area features a list of resources, with the first one titled "6 Res...". A payment form overlay is centered on the screen, containing the following fields and options:

- Customer location: United States (USD)
- Size: Desktop
- Theme: Default
- Payment methods: Card, Google Pay, Us bank account
- Card number: 1234 1234 1234 1234
- Expiration: MM / YY
- CVC: CVC

Below the payment form, two resource cards are visible, each for "100 Smart Street, LA, USA". Each card includes icons for a car (3), a wheelchair (1), a car (2), and a person (0), and is labeled "Apartment on Rent" and "For Long Period: 1 - 2 Years".

Finally, by clicking one of the resources a payment form will appear.